

STUDIES IN MICHAEL CONDENSATION. PART I.

BY SAILENDRA MOHAN MUKHERJEE AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

The condensation of crotonaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde with acetoacetic ester in presence of traces of sodium ethoxide furnished substituted *cyclohexanone* derivatives.

During the Michael condensation between an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated aldehyde and a reactive methylene group in presence of a basic catalyst, the elimination of a molecule of water is presumably the first step of a series of complex reactions as shown by Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 730; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1918, ii, 97, 288) Farmer and Mehta (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2561) and Meerwin (*Annalen.* 1904, 336, 339; 1908, 358, 71; 360, 327). But the normal Michael condensation between crotonaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde and acetoacetic ester was successfully carried out as described below.

Crotonaldehyde (I, R = Me) has been condensed with acetoacetic ester in alcoholic solution at -10° to -5° in presence of traces of sodium ethoxide to obtain (II, R = Me) together with a considerable portion of a higher boiling fraction. When the above reaction is carried out in presence of a molar quantity of sodium ethoxide, only the higher boiling product was formed in conformity with the observation of the above workers. The above compound (II, R = Me) is hydrogenated and the resulting compound (III, R = Me) hydrolysed and decarboxylated to yield *m*-methyl*cyclohexanone* (IV, R = Me) whose identity has been confirmed by the mixed m.p. of its semicarbazone with an authentic specimen of the same.

The above condensation has been carried out with cinnamaldehyde (I, R = Ph) to produce (II, III and IV where R = Ph).

The above reaction has been studied in order to prepare the intermediate compounds to build up the fully and partially hydrogenated *cyclopentano*-perhydrophenanthrene derivatives.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclohex-5-ene-1-one-2-carboxylate.—A solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.1 g.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) was taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury-sealed stirrer, thermometer and a dropping funnel and cooled in a freezing mixture. While the temperature of the alkoxide was falling, acetoacetic ester (27 g.) was poured in and the stirring was commenced. When the temperature of the reaction mixture was cooled down to -10° , a solution of freshly distilled crotonaldehyde (14 g.) in alcohol (90 c.c.) was added drop by drop. The stirring was stopped after the addition was complete. Towards the end the temperature of the content reached -5° . The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure (water-pump) when a red colour developed. The content was next poured into brine solution, extracted with ether, washed thrice with water and distilled under 6 mm. of pressure (a) $110-12^{\circ}$, (b) $112-4^{\circ}$, (c) $170-80^{\circ}$. On redistillation the following two main fractions were collected under 6 mm. of pressure, (1) $107-10^{\circ}$; (2) $165-72^{\circ}$. The first fraction contained the compound (II, R-Me) and gave greenish brown coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 7.6. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.6 per cent). Second fraction gave C, 66.6; H, 7.5%.

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate.—The above unsaturated compound (5 g.) was hydrogenated in alcoholic solution with Adam's catalyst (0.1 g.) when calculated quantity of hydrogen (500 c.c.) was absorbed. The catalyst was filtered and the solution was distilled, b.p. $122-25^{\circ}/16$ mm. A temporary violet coloration was obtained by treating the compound with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 8.5. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent).

m-Methylcyclohexanone.—The above compound. (III, R-Me) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 20% sulphuric acid for 16 hours. It was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and distilled. The fraction coming over at $160-80^{\circ}$ was collected and it furnished immediately a semi-carbazone. It was twice crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 172° , (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, $172-73^{\circ}$). (Found: N, 25.02. $C_9H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 24.85 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Phenylcyclohex-5-ene-1-one-2-carboxylate.—A solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.5 g.) and alcohol (120 c.c.) was cooled to -10° and ethyl acetoacetate (52 g.) was added to the alkoxide solution. Next, a solution of cinnamaldehyde (52 g.) in alcohol (40 c.c.) was added drop by drop to the mixture which was shaken constantly. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and then poured into brine solution and worked up as before, b.p. $162^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 17 g. It gave a red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.52; H, 6.45. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.77; H, 6.55 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Phenylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate.—The above compound was hydrogenated in acetic acid solution as before, b.p. $155^{\circ}/$ mm. It gave a violet

coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 72.91 ; H, 7.5. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 73.17 ; H, 7.31 per cent).

m-Phenylcyclohexanone.—The compound (III, R=Ph) was refluxed with 20% sulphuric acid to yield 3-phenylcyclohexanone, b.p. 140°/6mm. (Found : C, 82.41 ; H, 8.1. $C_{12}H_{14}O$ requires C, 82.72 ; H, 8.05 per cent).

The above ketone furnished a semicarbazone, m.p. 169°(Lit. m.p. 169-169.5° ; Boyd, Clifford and Prodeert, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1920, 117, 1389). (Found : C, 67.01 ; H, 7.1. $C_{13}H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 67.57 ; H, 7.57 per cent).

cycloHex-1-ene-1-aldehyde.—*cycloHex-1-ene-1-acid* chloride (15.5 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.) was dropped in a mixture of quinoline (28 g.) and hydrocyanic acid generated from potassium cyanide (26 g.) and sulphuric acid according to the method of Grosheintz and Fischer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2021). The reaction mixture was worked up also according to the above procedure, b.p. 76°/17 mm., yield 3.5 g. The aldehyde was very susceptible to aerial oxidation. It furnished a semicarbazone, m.p. 218° (decomp.) (Literature records m.p. 212-13°, Wallach and Isaac, *Annalen*, 1906, 347, 337). (Found : N, 24.6. $C_8O_{13}ON_3$ requires N 25.15 per cent).

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SIR P. C. RAY RESEARCH FELLOW'S LABORATORY
AND
PALIT LABORATORY OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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